

Improving the performance of photoelectrochemical CO reduction through ethylene glycol oxidation

Janusz Kotowicz, Dominik Hulak*, Leszek Remiorz, Mateusz Brzęczek, Łukasz Böhm, Oliwia Baszczęńska, Katarzyna Janusz-Szymańska, Kamil Niesporek

^aSilesian University of Technology, Department of Power Engineering and Turbomachinery, Konarskiego 18, 44-100, Gliwice, Poland

Abstract

Electrochemical CO reduction (ECOR) is emerging as a sustainable alternative fuel production method to conventional methods and CO₂ electrolysis. The reaction is most often coupled with oxygen evolution reaction (OER), which is energy-intensive and produces low-value product. To improve the system feasibility, we investigate replacing OER with ethylene glycol oxidation reaction (EGOR), which promises lower energy consumption, produces added-value glycolic acid and enables the recycling of waste PET. To achieve this, we compare CO electrolysis systems based on OER and EGOR. To achieve this, we propose and validate a simplified modelling framework. First, we give insight into the operation of the OER and EGOR based systems. When using modern EGOR catalyst, the voltage reduction exceeds 0.5 V, which translates into a 16% decrease in the reactor's energy consumption at 400 mA cm⁻². Next, we investigate the attractiveness of EGOR in solar-based systems in PV-EC, PEC and PV-PEC configurations. Due to the lower anodic potential, it enables the unbiased solar-based systems to operate at current densities exceeding 10 mA cm⁻², marking a significant improvement versus OER based systems. The use of EGOR enabled an upcycling of PET-derived ethylene glycol at significant rate.

Keywords: Electrochemical reduction, solar fuels, renewable energy, PET recycling, CO electrolysis, ethylene glycol

*Corresponding author

Email address: dominik.hulak@polsl.pl (Dominik Hulak)

1. Introduction

The transition to a low-carbon energy system requires new technologies capable of producing sustainable fuels. Currently, one of the most promising technologies is electrochemical CO₂ reduction (ECO₂R) using Cu electrodes [1]. It enables the production of fuels such as ethylene [2], ethanol and propanol [3], as well as a range of chemicals of industrial interest [4, 5]. Furthermore, when using captured CO₂, the technology can achieve carbon neutrality. However, this process is currently facing a number of challenges, with the key issue being (bi)carbonate formation, which decreases the single-pass conversion rate and may lead to salt precipitation in alkaline media [6–8].

Since CO does not react with the formed OH⁻ ions, electrochemical CO reduction (ECOR) is a possible path for carbonate-free production of fuels. Numerous studies have demonstrated the advantages of ECOR over ECO₂R for the production of C₂₊ compounds [9–11]. However, the low solubility of CO (≈ 1 mM [12]) limits the achievable current densities, even more so than in the case of CO₂ (≈ 34 mM [13]). For H-type cells, the limiting current is below 5 mA cm⁻² [1, 12, 14]. The strategies for improving mass transfer conditions are similar to those used in ECO₂R - the use of flow cells and gas diffusion electrodes (GDE) [11, 15]. These help achieve current densities in excess of 300-500 mA cm⁻², with total selectivities towards C₂₊ products exceeding 70-80% [9–11, 15, 16]. To decrease the energy consumption, GDEs are often deployed in zero-gap or membrane-electrode assembly (MEA) systems, which provide lower resistance [15, 17].

In order for ECOR to be considered a sustainable method of fuel production, it must be powered using renewable energy. The use of solar energy is of particular interest [18–21] and it enables the production of so-called solar fuels. However, modern Si solar cells (SiSC) and perovskite solar cells (PSC) achieve voltages that are too low (<0.8 V and <1.3 V, respectively [22–24]) to carry out unbiased ECOR at appreciable current densities. The voltage can be increased by using an external cell array (PV-EC configuration [25, 26]), or by connecting an external solar cell with photoelectrode in series (PEC configuration [20, 21]).

In order to reduce the required cell voltage, the anodic oxygen evolution reaction (OER) can be replaced with reactions more favourable from a thermodynamic point of view [21, 27, 28]. One promising candidate is the ethylene glycol oxidation reaction (EGOR). Pd- and Ni-based catalysts have demonstrated high selectivity towards glycolic acid, with minor production of oxalic acid and formate [29–32]. The onset potential of EGOR is 1 V lower than OER [29, 30], what may enable the cooperation with SiSC and PSC.

The added benefit of using EGOR is the possibility of PET recycling. Ethylene glycol is a monomer of PET and can be obtained by its alkaline hydrolysis [33]. Given the global annual production on the order of 70 million tons and relatively low recycling rates [34], EGOR-based ECOR can reduce the environmental impact of PET.

Modelling is a useful tool for studying these types of systems, which differ in terms of power supply, mass transport conditions, catalyst type and process parameters. At present, the most comprehensive models are related to ECO_2R [35–38], and only a minority of works regard ECOR [39, 40]. These studies are most often based on computationally demanding, multiphysics simulations. This type of modelling is rarely used in feasibility evaluation and life cycle assessment. To guide the design of systems and to assess them, simplified models are practically needed. Models of this type are commonly used in water electrolysis [41–43] for example.

In this work, we investigate EGOR-assisted CO electrolysis as a method for production of renewable solar fuels. To achieve this, we present a simplified model for ECOR to C_{2+} products in a GDE-based flow-cell reactor. It captures the essential electrochemical (OER or EGOR) and mass transfer processes without the need for computationally-demanding multiphysics simulations. Verification was performed based on literature data. Based on our simulations, we provide insight into the operation of the ECOR systems in various non-solar and solar-driven configurations. We demonstrate, that the use of ethylene glycol oxidation has the potential to improve the performance of ECOR by (a) reducing the required cell voltage in industrial applications or (b) enabling standalone solar-driven systems to operate at significantly higher current densities.

2. Methods

In this section, a set of equations describing the system is presented, the key assumptions are explained and the simplifications are justified. The diagram of the system in its different configurations is demonstrated in Figure 1. A typical flow reactor

Figure 1: (a) Diagram of the externally-biased, gas-fed flow cell. (b) PV-EC system. (c) PEC system in two-electrode configuration. (d) PV-PEC system.

(Figure 1a) consists of a cathode (GDE) and an anode (non-GDE) separated by a membrane and electrolyte layers. The feed CO is distributed via the flow field plate. Reactant then diffuses through the GDE to the catalyst, where the reactions take place at the catalyst/electrolyte interface. The main products of CO reduction on Cu electrodes are

hydrocarbons and hydrogen from the parasitic hydrogen evolution reaction (HER).

Electrons from the cathode participate in the reactions. It can be assumed that the gaseous products diffuse back through the GDE to the flow plate, from where they are removed together with unreacted CO. In turn, liquid products remain in the solution and are removed from the reactor together with the catholyte.

The OH^- ions formed in the cathodic reactions diffuse through the membrane to the anode. On the surface of the catalyst OER takes place. Produced O_2 bubbles into the anolyte solution and the charge is transferred to the electrode.

The current flow through the cell occurs as a result of applying an external voltage U_{cell} . In an unbiased solar-driven systems, the necessary voltage is provided by solar cells. These can be photovoltaic cells in PV-EC (Figure 1b), photoelectrode in PEC (Figure 1c) or their combination in PV-PEC (Figure 1d). The simplest layout here is PV-EC, as the reactor itself does not undergo any modifications. In order for the system to operate in PEC configuration, it is necessary to use appropriate photocatalysts. These are most often deployed in two-electrode systems, with direct photoelectrode illumination. In this case, the limiting factor is the solubility of CO. In order to use the GDE-based flow cell, back-illuminated photoelectrodes may be better suited. These however, due to the larger charger diffusion length, perform poorer compared to front-illuminated cells [44]. To increase the voltage and improve the performance, the photoelectrode may be connected in series with semi-transparent PV cell (Figure 1d).

If no external bias is applied and the solar cells are connected in series, then $U_{cell} = U_{pa} + U_{PV}$. U_{cell} depends on the reversible voltage E_{rev} , cathodic η_c and anodic η_a overpotentials and ohmic losses U_{Ω} ,

$$U_{cell} = E_{rev} + \eta_a + |\eta_c| + U_{\Omega}. \quad (1)$$

By convention, the cathodic overpotential η_c is negative, hence the absolute value in equation (1). E_{rev} is defined as the difference between reversible potentials of the anode $E_{rev,a}$ and the cathode $E_{rev,c}$,

$$E_{rev} = E_{rev,a} - E_{rev,c}. \quad (2)$$

This equation is typically applied when a single reaction occurs at the electrodes. In

cases where multiple reactions are considered, each of them is characterized by its own E_{rev} . Values of $E_{rev,a}$ and $E_{rev,c}$ can be determined using the Nernst equation

$$E_{rev,a} = E_a^0 - \frac{R_{gas}T}{z_a F} \ln Q_a, \quad (3)$$

$$E_{rev,c} = E_c^0 - \frac{R_{gas}T}{z_c F} \ln Q_c, \quad (4)$$

where E^0 is the standard electrode potential, z is the number of electrons transferred in the reaction, Q is the reaction quotient, T is the temperature, $F = 98465 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$ is the Faraday's constant, and $R = 8,314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ is the universal gas constant. Standard electrode potentials E^0 are determined for a temperature T of 298.15 K, gas pressures p of 1 atm and solute concentrations C of 1 M. The values of E^0 and z are collected in Table 1.

Table 1: Values of E^0 and z for selected reactions.

Reaction	E^0 , V vs. SHE	z
$2 \text{ H}_2\text{O} + 2 \text{ e}^- \rightarrow \text{H}_2 + 2 \text{ OH}^-$ (HER)	0	2
$2 \text{ CO} + 4 \text{ H}_2\text{O} + 4 \text{ e}^- \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{COOH} + 4 \text{ OH}^-$	0.28	4
$\text{CO} + 5 \text{ H}_2\text{O} + 6 \text{ e}^- \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + 6 \text{ OH}^-$	0.26	6
$2 \text{ CO} + 6 \text{ H}_2\text{O} + 8 \text{ e}^- \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_4 + 8 \text{ OH}^-$	0.19	8
$2 \text{ CO} + 7 \text{ H}_2\text{O} + 8 \text{ e}^- \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} + 8 \text{ OH}^-$	0.17	8
$3 \text{ CO} + 8 \text{ H}_2\text{O} + 10 \text{ e}^- \rightarrow \text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O} + 10 \text{ OH}^-$	0.14	10
$3 \text{ CO} + 10 \text{ H}_2\text{O} + 12 \text{ e}^- \rightarrow \text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH} + 12 \text{ OH}^-$	0.20	12
$4 \text{ OH}^- \rightarrow \text{O}_2 + 2 \text{ H}_2\text{O} + 4 \text{ e}^-$	1.23	4
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}_2 + 4 \text{ OH}^- \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_3 + 3 \text{ H}_2\text{O} + 4 \text{ e}^-$	-0.34	4

While E_{rev} is the minimum voltage required for a reaction to occur under given conditions, its intensity depends on the overpotential. According to the Tafel equation,

$$i^\phi = \pm i_0^\phi \cdot \exp\left(\pm \frac{\alpha^\phi F \eta^\phi}{R_{gas}T}\right), \phi = \text{H}_2, \text{CH}_4, \text{O}_2, \dots, \quad (5)$$

where i^ϕ is the partial current density towards substance ϕ , i_0^ϕ is the exchange current density and α^ϕ is the charge transfer coefficient. The \pm sign in equation (5) is + for

anodic and – for cathodic products. It is assumed that i^X denotes cathodic gas products (e.g. i^{H_2} or $i^{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4}$) and i^Y denotes cathodic liquid products (e.g. $i^{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}}$ or $i^{\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}}$). The only anodic product in OER is oxygen with a partial current density i^{O_2} . Then it can be stated that

$$i = i^{\text{O}_2} = \left| \sum_X i^X + \sum_Y i^Y \right|. \quad (6)$$

where i is the total current density.

The analysis of equations (5) shows that as η increases, the current density increases exponentially. This would only be possible if the substrate concentration did not decrease in the catalytic zone. In reality, as i increases, the concentration decreases and exponential growth is not possible. This effect of limiting current density is captured in the concentration-dependent Tafel equation [39]

$$i^\phi = \pm i_0^\phi \left(\frac{C}{C_{ref}} \right)^{\gamma^\phi} \cdot \exp \left(\pm \frac{\alpha^\phi F \eta^\phi}{R_{gas} T} \right), \quad (7)$$

where C is the substrate concentration near the catalyst, C_{ref} is the reference substrate concentration and γ^ϕ is the reaction order. In this model, it is assumed that C_{ref} is calculated for $i = 0$.

The values of i_0^ϕ have been fit to the experimental data for one given temperature T . For $T' \neq T$, the following equation holds true

$$i_0^\phi(T') = i_0^\phi(T) \cdot \exp \left[\frac{-E_a^\phi}{R_{gas}} \left(\frac{1}{T'} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right], \quad (8)$$

where E_a^ϕ is the activation energy. For oxygen, $E_a^{\text{O}_2}$ is assumed to be 10 kJ mol^{-1} , and 100 kJ mol^{-1} for cathodic products.

2.1. Mass balance

In order to determine the concentration values in equation (7) and the reaction quotients in equations (3) and (4), a simplified mass transport model is proposed herein. The starting point for its creation is the mass balance, and its diagram is shown in Figure 2a.

There are eight main layers of the reactor – flow field (FF), gas diffusion electrode (GDE), cathode boundary layer (C-BL), cathode electrolyte (C-EL), membrane (M),

Figure 2: (a) Mass flow diagram of the cell. (b) Close-up diagram of the mass flow in the GDE.

anode electrolyte (A-EL), anode boundary layer (A-BL) and anode (A). Furthermore, the GDE consists of three sublayers (Figure 2b), that is a gas diffusion layer (GDL), microporous layer (MPL) and a catalyst layer (C-CL).

The streams fed into the reactor are: the CO stream to FF and the aqueous electrolyte streams to C-EL and A-EL. For CO, the inlet flow $\dot{n}_{in,FF}^{CO}$ is determined based on the defined volumetric flow $\dot{V}_{in,FF}^{CO}$ as

$$\dot{n}_{in,FF}^{CO} = \dot{V}_{in,FF}^{CO} C_{in,FF}^{CO}, \quad (9)$$

where $C_{in,FF}^{CO}$ is the inlet CO concentration. As a result of the reactions, a portion of the substrate $\dot{n}_{in,GDE}^{CO}$ is reduced, while the remaining amount exits the cathode as unreacted flow $\dot{n}_{out,FF}^{CO} = \dot{n}_{in,FF}^{CO} - \dot{n}_{in,GDE}^{CO}$. The amount of CO diffusing into the GDE can be expressed as

$$\dot{n}_{in,GDE}^{CO} = \sum_X \psi_X^{CO} \dot{n}_{gen}^X + \sum_Y \psi_Y^{CO} \dot{n}_{gen}^Y, \quad (10)$$

where \dot{n}_{gen}^X and \dot{n}_{gen}^Y are the molar flows of products generated as a result of CO reduction ($X \neq H_2$) in gaseous and liquid form, respectively, and ψ^{CO} is the stoichiometric coefficient determining the number of moles of CO per mole of generated product (e.g. $\psi_{CH_4}^{CO} = 1$, $\psi_{C_2H_4}^{CO} = 2$; see Table 1). The generated molar flow of a product \dot{n}_{gen} is described as

$$\dot{n}_{gen} = \frac{Ai}{zF}, \quad (11)$$

where A is the cell cross-section area. The streams of generated gas products are also the outlet streams $\dot{n}_{gen}^X = \dot{n}_{out,FF}^X$, and therefore the total volumetric flow rate at the FF outlet $\dot{V}_{out,FF}$ is given by,

$$\dot{V}_{out,FF} = \frac{(\dot{n}_{out,FF}^{CO} + \sum_X \dot{n}_{gen}^X) R_{gas} T}{p_c}, \quad (12)$$

where p_c is the cathodic pressure. A similar mass balance is carried out for the C-EL layer. At the inlet to the C-EL, the electrolyte concentration $C_{in,C-EL}^{MOH}$ and the total volumetric flow rate $\dot{V}_{in,C-EL}$ are known. In this case, the molar flow rate of the electrolyte can be defined as

$$\dot{n}_{in,C-EL}^{MOH} = \dot{V}_{in,C-EL} C_{in,C-EL}^{MOH}. \quad (13)$$

The inlet molar flow rate of water $\dot{n}_{in,C-EL}^{H_2O}$ is determined from the molar balance of a binary solution as

$$\dot{n}_{in,C-EL}^{H_2O} = \dot{V}_{in,C-EL} \frac{\rho_{in,C-EL} - C_{in,C-EL}^{MOH} M^{MOH}}{M^{H_2O}} \quad (14)$$

where $\rho_{in,C-EL}$ is the inlet solution density and M^{MOH} , M^{H_2O} are molar masses of electrolyte and water, respectively.

Assuming, that no water is transported through the membrane, the molar balance of the water in C-EL layer is described as

$$\dot{n}_{out,C-EL}^{H_2O} = \dot{n}_{in,C-EL}^{H_2O} - \dot{n}_{out,GDE}^{H_2O}, \quad (15)$$

where $\dot{n}_{out,C-EL}^{H_2O}$ is the outflow and $\dot{n}_{in,GDE}^{H_2O}$ is the amount transported to the GDE. The quantity $\dot{n}_{in,GDE}^{H_2O}$ is equal to the amount of water consumed in the cathodic reactions $\dot{n}_{cons}^{H_2O}$, as described by

$$\dot{n}_{cons}^{H_2O} = \sum_X \psi_X^{H_2O} \dot{n}_{gen}^X + \sum_Y \psi_Y^{H_2O} \dot{n}_{gen}^Y. \quad (16)$$

where ψ^{H_2O} are the stoichiometric coefficients describing the number of moles of H_2O consumed per mole of generated product (e.g. $\psi_{C_2H_4}^{H_2O} = 6$). In addition to water, the outlet stream contains electrolyte and liquid products. It was assumed that the electrolyte outlet stream $\dot{n}_{out,C-EL}^{MOH} = \dot{n}_{in,C-EL}^{MOH}$, and that the outlet product streams $\dot{n}_{out,C-EL}^Y$ are equal to generated streams \dot{n}_{gen}^Y , as determined by equation (11).

Due to the presence of additional reaction products in the outlet stream, determination of its density $\rho_{out,C-EL}$ is more challenging. It was therefore assumed that $\rho_{out,C-EL} = \rho_{in,C-EL}$. This is justified as the product streams are relatively small and the impact on density is negligible [17]. Then, the C-EL outlet volumetric flow $\dot{V}_{out,C-EL}$ can be defined as

$$\dot{V}_{out,C-EL} = \frac{\dot{n}_{out,C-EL}^{H_2O} + \dot{n}_{out,C-EL}^{MOH} + \sum_Y \dot{n}_{out,C-EL}^Y M^Y}{\rho_{out,C-EL}} \quad (17)$$

Lastly, the mass balance is carried out for the A-EL layer. However, the procedure is almost identical as for C-EL. The inlet molar flow rate of the anolyte $\dot{n}_{in,A-EL}^{MOH}$ is calculated using equation (13), but for $\dot{V}_{in,A-EL}$ and $C_{in,A-EL}^{MOH}$. Then the inlet density $\rho_{in,A-EL}$ is determined via adequate correlation, which is in turn used to calculate inlet water stream $\dot{n}_{in,A-EL}^{H_2O}$ using modified equation (14). It is again assumed that $\rho_{out,A-EL} = \rho_{in,A-EL}$ and $\dot{n}_{out,A-EL}^{MOH} = \dot{n}_{in,A-EL}^{MOH}$. The anodic water balance is

$$\dot{n}_{out,A-EL}^{H_2O} = \dot{n}_{in,A-EL}^{H_2O} + \dot{n}_{out,A}^{H_2O} \quad (18)$$

where the stream of water exiting the anode $\dot{n}_{out,A}^{H_2O}$ is equal to the stream generated $\dot{n}_{gen}^{H_2O}$. Then the outlet volumetric flow $\dot{V}_{out,A-EL}$ is calculated as

$$\dot{V}_{out,A-EL} = \frac{\dot{n}_{out,A-EL}^{H_2O} M^{H_2O} + \dot{n}_{out,A-EL}^{MOH} M^{MOH}}{\rho_{out,A-EL}}. \quad (19)$$

The formed O_2 is neglected in equation (19) as it bubbles out and is not dissolved in the solution. Nonetheless, the stream of generated oxygen $\dot{n}_{gen}^{O_2}$ is described by equation (11). This is accompanied by a generated stream of water $\dot{n}_{gen}^{H_2O} = 2\dot{n}_{gen}^{O_2}$.

The last stream considered in the reactor is the OH^- ion stream \dot{n}^{OH^-} . It is defined as

$$\dot{n}^{OH^-} = \frac{Ai_a}{F} = -\frac{Ai_c}{F}. \quad (20)$$

As it is the only charge carrier in the cell, it is both the molar stream produced at the cathode and consumed at the anode. In this model, it is assumed that the reactor operates in a steady state, and therefore OH^- ions from the electrolyte are not consumed at the anode.

2.2. Inlet and outlet concentrations

The only concentration values assumed in the model are the inlet concentrations of electrolytes C_{in}^{MOH} . The remaining concentrations that need to be calculated are the inlet concentrations of CO and water, as well as the outlet concentrations of unreacted CO, water, electrolytes and reaction products.

The inlet CO concentration $C_{in,FF}^{CO}$ needs to be specified to calculate $\dot{n}_{in,FF}^{CO}$ via equation (9). Based on the ideal gas law

$$C_{in,FF}^{CO} = \frac{p_c}{R_{gas}T}, \quad (21)$$

where p_c is the cathodic pressure. Knowing the value of $\dot{n}_{in,FF}^{CO}$, a full mass balance can be performed in accordance with the previous section. Using the specified molar \dot{n} and volumetric \dot{V} flow rates, the inlet C_{in} or outlet C_{out} concentration of any species can be determined by

$$C_{in} = \frac{\dot{n}_{in}}{\dot{V}_{in}}, \quad (22)$$

$$C_{out} = \frac{\dot{n}_{out}}{\dot{V}_{out}}. \quad (23)$$

The concentrations determined in this way will be further used to determine the concentrations in the reactor's catalytic layers.

2.3. Bulk and layer concentrations

The notation used to identify concentrations in individual layers, their interfaces and the concentration profiles, is shown in Figure 3a. In the FF, C-EL and A-EL layers, the bulk concentrations of species are constant and equal to arithmetic means between inlet and outlet values (e.g. $C_{FF} = 0.5 [C_{in,FF} + C_{out,FF}]$). Since inlet product concentrations are zero, their bulk concentration are equal to $0.5C_{out,FF}$. In turn, the concentrations of OH^- ions in C-EL and A-EL is determined based on the pH values of the inlet streams as,

$$C_{C-EL}^{OH^-} = 10^{pH_{in,C-EL}-14} \quad (24)$$

$$C_{A-EL}^{OH^-} = 10^{pH_{in,A-EL}-14} \quad (25)$$

Figure 3: (a) Species concentrations in the cell. (b) Species concentrations in the GDE.

where $\text{pH}_{in,C-EL}$ and $\text{pH}_{in,A-EL}$ are the pH at the inlets of C-EL and A-EL, respectively.

It is assumed that mass transport through the boundary layers and the GDE is governed by Fick's diffusion law

$$\dot{n} = D \frac{\Delta C}{\sigma} A, \quad (26)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient, ΔC is the concentration difference and σ is the thickness of diffusion layer (see Figures 3a and 3b). The values of D for relevant aqueous species and cell dimensions A and σ are listed in Table 2. The procedure for determining binary diffusion coefficients for gases is described in Supplementary Note 1. The equation (26) can be used to calculate the concentration of species at the anode surface C_A , cathode surface C_{GDE} , GDL/MPL interface $C_{GDL/MPL}$ and MPL/C-CL interface $C_{MPL/C-CL}$. In a flow configuration, the thickness of the electrolyte layer in a half-cell (σ_{C-EL} , σ_{A-EL}) is usually in the range of 1-3 mm, and its boundary layer thickness is typically between 50 and 150 μm . In the case of a zero-gap half-cell with electrolyte flow through the porous electrode, it is assumed that the electrolyte thickness is 0 and the boundary layer is much smaller - on the order of 10 μm .

While it is assumed that the anodic reactions take place on the anode surface, the cathodic reactions take place in the volume of C-CL. In order to describe mass transport in the C-CL layer, a diffusion-reaction model was adopted instead of equation (26). It

Table 2: Diffusion coefficients and cell geometry.

Parameter	Value	Ref.
D^{OH^-}	$5.273 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	[10]
$D^{\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}}$	$1.19 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	[45]
$D^{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_3}$	$1.194 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	[46]
$D^{\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}}$	$1.00 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	[45]
$D^{\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}_2}$	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	[47]
$D^{\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O}}$	$0.90 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	[45]
$D^{\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}}$	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	[48]
A	1 cm^2	[17]
σ_{GDL}	$205 \mu\text{m}$	[49]
σ_{MPL}	$10 \mu\text{m}$	[17]
$\sigma_{\text{C-CL}}$	$2 \mu\text{m}$	[17]
$\sigma_{\text{C-EL}}$	2.5 mm	[17]
$\sigma_{\text{C-BL}}$	$100 \mu\text{m}$	Assumption
$\sigma_{\text{A-EL}}$	0	[17]
$\sigma_{\text{A-BL}}$	$10 \mu\text{m}$	Assumption
$\varepsilon_{\text{C-CL}}$	0.5	Assumption
r_{MPL}	$0.05 \mu\text{m}$	Assumption
$r_{\text{C-CL}}$	$0.05 \mu\text{m}$	Assumption
$\sigma_{\text{C-CL}}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$0.005 \mu\text{m}$	Assumption

is described by the differential equation

$$0 = D \frac{d^2 C}{d\sigma^2} \pm \frac{\dot{n}}{V} \quad (27)$$

where \dot{n}/V describes the volumetric reaction rate. The sign in equation (27) is positive for the products and negative for the substrates. For gaseous products, V represents the pore volume of CL-C filled with gas V_{gas} , while for OH^- and liquid products it is the pore volume filled with liquid V_{liquid} . Their values are defined as

$$V_{gas} = \varepsilon_{C-CL} \sigma_{C-CL} A \left(\frac{r_{C-CL} - \sigma_{C-CL}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{r_{C-CL}} \right)^2, \quad (28)$$

$$V_{liquid} = \varepsilon_{C-CL} \sigma_{C-CL} A \left[1 - \left(\frac{r_{C-CL} - \sigma_{C-CL}^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{r_{C-CL}} \right)^2 \right], \quad (29)$$

where ε_{C-CL} is the C-CL porosity, r_{C-CL} is the C-CL pore radius and σ_{C-CL} is the thickness of water layer covering the inner walls of C-CL. Equations (28) and (29) were derived assuming that the above parameters are constant for the entire thickness of the layer.

By integrating equation (27) twice, a function describing the concentration profile of reactants in C-CL is obtained

$$C(\sigma) = \mp \frac{\dot{n}}{2DV} \sigma^2 + \mathbb{C}_1 \sigma + \mathbb{C}_2, \quad (30)$$

where \mathbb{C}_1 and \mathbb{C}_2 are the integration constants. For gaseous species, the boundary conditions are $C_{C-CL}(\sigma = 0) = C_{MPL/C-CL}$ and $-D \frac{dC}{d\sigma} |_{\sigma=\sigma_{C-CL}} = 0$, and for aqueous species they are $C_{C-CL}(\sigma = \sigma_{C-CL}) = C_{GDE/C-CL}$ and $-D \frac{dC}{d\sigma} |_{\sigma=0} = 0$.

Using equation (30), the average concentration of reactants in the C-CL layer can be determined as

$$C_{C-CL} = \frac{1}{\sigma_{C-CL}} \int_0^{\sigma_{C-CL}} C(\sigma) d\sigma. \quad (31)$$

It describes the concentration of liquids in the water layer (in contact with the catalyst) and gases in the free pore volume (not in contact). When determining concentrations of gases on the catalyst, it is more convenient to use partial pressures. For ideal gases they are defined as

$$p_{C-CL} = C_{C-CL}^{\text{CO}} R_{gas} T. \quad (32)$$

The concentration of CO dissolved in water $C_{diss,C-CL}^{CO}$ is defined by Henry's constant H^{CO} and can be calculated as,

$$C_{diss,C-CL}^{CO} = H^{CO} p_{C-CL}^{CO} 10^{-K_s}. \quad (33)$$

The value of H^{CO} is described by the relation [50]

$$H^{CO} = 9.7 \cdot 10^{-6} \exp \left[1300 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{298.15} \right) \right]. \quad (34)$$

However, H^{CO} determined via (34) specifies solubility in pure water. Solubility is however lower in aqueous electrolyte solutions, due to the salting-out effect. To account for it, the Sechenov's constant K_s can be used [51], as in equation (33). Its value is here defined as

$$K_s = C_{C-CL}^{OH^-} k_s^{OH^-} + C_{C-CL}^{M^+} k_s^{M^+}, \quad (35)$$

where $k_s^{OH^-}$ and $k_s^{M^+}$ are ion-specific Sechenov constants, and $C_{C-CL}^{K^+}$ is the concentration of electrolyte cations in the catalysts layer, which is assumed to be equal to $C_{in,C-EL}^{MOH}$. The equation (35) would normally take into account the gas-specific Sechenov constant k_s^{CO} . However, its value is unavailable in the literature, but since k_s values are typically much higher for ions than for gases, omitting it does not introduce a significant error.

The concentration calculated via equation (33) can be converted back to partial pressure as

$$p_{diss,C-CL}^{CO} = C_{diss,C-CL}^{CO} R_{gas} T. \quad (36)$$

The dissolution of gases other than CO is not considered, as these form bubbles on the surface of the catalyst and quickly escape the system. The partial pressure of gaseous products in the catalyst zone were therefore determined as bubble pressures, described as

$$p_{bubble,C-CL}^X = \frac{p_{C-CL}^X}{\sum_X p_{C-CL}^X} \cdot p_c. \quad (37)$$

At this point, all values enabling the determination of equations (3), (4) and (7) are known.

2.4. Ohmic losses

One of the components of equation (1) is U_Ω . The ohmic losses of the cell are described, in accordance with Ohm's law, by the relation

$$U_\Omega = R_{cell}i_a A = -R_{cell}i_c A, \quad (38)$$

where R_{cell} is the cell resistance, equal to the sum of the resistances of the components R in a series configuration [41]. In general, R of a rectangular element with cross-section A and thickness σ can be described in terms of its resistivity λ , conductivity κ or area-specific resistance ASR as

$$R = \lambda \frac{\sigma}{A} = \frac{\sigma}{\kappa A} = \frac{ASR}{A}. \quad (39)$$

Between λ and κ there is a dependence $\lambda = 1/\kappa$, and typically one of the values is provided. On the other hand, the thickness-independent ASR is commonly used by GDL manufacturers [49, 52] and when incorporating contact resistance [53].

The resistance of the flow field plate R_{FF} can be expressed as the sum of the base resistance $R_{b,FF}$ and the channel resistance $R_{ch,FF}$ [54]

$$R_{FF} = R_{b,FF} + R_{ch,FF}. \quad (40)$$

Flow field plates are typically made out of stainless steel coated with a protective layer. Due to small thickness of this layer, λ_{FF} was assumed as for stainless steel. Equation (39) can be used directly to calculate $R_{b,FF}$. However, when determining $R_{ch,FF}$, the geometry of the flow channels must be taken into account. For a flow plate with n_{FF} channels, $R_{ch,FF}$ can be calculated as

$$R_{ch,FF} = \frac{\lambda_{FF} \sigma_{ch,FF}}{2A \frac{n_{FF}+1}{2n_{FF}+1}}, \quad (41)$$

under the assumption that the height of a flow field is equal to \sqrt{A} and that the height of each channel is equal to that of the channel support.

For a three-layer GDE, its resistance R_{GDE} can be determined using the transformed relationship (39) as

$$R_{GDE} = \frac{\sigma_{GDL}}{\kappa_{GDL}A} + \frac{\sigma_{MPL}}{\kappa_{MPL}A} + \frac{\sigma_{C-CL}}{\kappa_{C-CL}A}. \quad (42)$$

For known σ_{GDL} and ASR, it is true that $\kappa_{\text{GDL}} = \sigma_{\text{GDL}}/\text{ASR}_{\text{GDL}}$. The resistance data for MPL and C-CL is less readily available, so they values of κ have been estimated based on [53]. Additional contact resistance R_{cont} occurs between GDE layers, as well as between GDE and FF. Value of R_{cont} does not depend on the thickness of the elements. It is then determined based on experimental ASR [53] and can be calculated directly using equation (39).

The resistance of catholyte $R_{\text{C-EL}}$ and anolyte $R_{\text{A-EL}}$ can also be calculated from equation (39). It should be remembered that the conductivity of electrolytes κ^{MOH} is a function of electrolyte concentration [55, 56]. For simplicity, it was assumed that κ^{MOH} is determined for the inlet concentrations and its change due to the concentration gradient is ignored. If given electrode is in direct contact with the membrane, the resistance of its electrolyte layer is assumed to be 0. In that case, however, the additional contact resistance ($R_{\text{C-CL/M}}$ or $R_{\text{M/A}}$) is included.

The membrane resistance R_{M} can also be determined directly from equation (39). In this case, the ionic conductivity of the membrane κ_{M} must be taken into account.

While in the mass transport model, the anode was assumed to be planar, in the resistance model it is considered to be a porous medium. Its resistance R_{A} consists of the resistance of the solid electrode material $R_{\text{solid,A}}$ and the in-pore liquid electrolyte $R_{\text{liquid,A}}$. The resistance $R_{\text{solid,A}}$ is governed by

$$R_{\text{solid,A}} = \lambda_{\text{eff,A}} \frac{\sigma_{\text{A}}}{A}, \quad (43)$$

where $\lambda_{\text{eff,A}}$ is the effective resistivity of the anode. For a medium with a porosity ε_{A} , the effective resistivity can be determined using

$$\lambda_{\text{eff,A}} = \frac{\lambda_{\text{A}}}{(1 - \varepsilon_{\text{A}})^{3/2}} \quad (44)$$

where λ_{A} is the resistivity of non-porous anode material. In turn, the resistance $R_{\text{liquid,A}}$ can be determined as [57]

$$R_{\text{liquid,A}} = \frac{\xi_{\text{A}} \sigma_{\text{A}}}{\varepsilon_{\text{A}} \kappa^{\text{MOH}}_{\text{A}}}, \quad (45)$$

where ξ_{A} is the anode tortuosity. The porous layer parameters ε and ξ can be related to each other according to Bruggeman's Law [58] as

$$\xi = \varepsilon^{3/2}. \quad (46)$$

The parameters used in ohmic losses calculations are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Resistance model parameters.

Parameter	Value	Ref.
n_{FF}	33	[17]
$\sigma_{b,FF}$	1 mm	Assumption
$\sigma_{ch,FF}$	90 μm	[17]
λ_{FF}	77 $\text{m}\Omega \text{ cm}$ (@ 25°C)	[59]
ASR_{GDL}	10 $\text{m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$	[49]
κ_{MPL}	30 S m^{-1}	[53]
κ_{C-CL}	15 S m^{-1}	[53]
κ^{NaOH}	16.3 S m^{-1} (@ 1 M)	[60]
κ_M	0.05 S cm^{-1}	[61]
σ_A	1.5 mm	[17]
λ_A	6.9 $\mu\Omega \text{ cm}$ (@ 20°C)	[62]
ε_A	0.93	[62]
$ASR_{FF/GDL}$	8 $\text{m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$	[53]
$ASR_{GDL/MPL}$	2 $\text{m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$	[53]
$ASR_{MPL/C-CL}$	3 $\text{m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$	[53]
$ASR_{M/A}$	8 $\text{m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$	Assumption

2.5. Model of PV components

To model the current–voltage characteristics of PV elements, equivalent circuit models are commonly used [63–65]. In this work, the equivalent circuit described by the equation

$$i = i_{sc} - i_d - i_{sh} = i_{sc} - i_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{q(U + iR_s)}{nkT}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{U + iR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (47)$$

was deployed. In (47), i_{sc} is the short-circuit current, i_0 is the dark current, $q = 1.6022 \cdot 10^{-19}$ C is the elementary charge, U is the element voltage, R_s is the series resistance, R_{sh} is the shunt resistance, n is the ideality factor and $k = 1.380 \cdot 10^{-23}$ J K⁻¹ is the Boltzmann constant.

In the cell arrangements shown in Figures 1b to 1d, i.e. with the components connected in series, the same current flows through each of them $I_{cell} = I_{PV} = I_{pa}$. When the surface area of the reactor cell is equal to the surface area of the solar cells, the current densities also follow $i_{cell} = i_{PV} = i_{pa}$.

In this model, it is assumed that when solar cell operates in reverse bias, the component in question is bypassed. If two or more solar cells are connected in series, they are bypassed when the entire series operates in reverse bias.

3. Results and discussion

Literature-based experimental data from [17] was used to verify the model assumptions. This analysis was chosen because, unlike most works on flow-cells (where only the half-cell potential is usually given), the full cell voltages are also provided. This allows for simultaneous validation of voltage-current characteristics and extraction of kinetic data.

The parameters collected in Tables 1 to 3 were used. The OER Tafel slope and onset potential η_{10} were extracted from the original linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) data of the NiFe catalyst [66], and then used to calculate i_0 and α . The flow of CO was 1 sccm and 1 M NaOH was used as the electrolytes, with volumetric flows of 150 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$. The cathodic values of α , i_0 and γ were fitted to the experimental data. The simulations were carried out using MATLAB software.

The results of the verification are presented in Figure 4. Good agreement can be observed between the experimental and simulated partial current densities for both the major (Figure 4a) and minor (Figure 4b) ECOR products. The best fit was obtained for the fuels of interest - C_2H_4 , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ and $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$. Methane, another fuel, shows poorer fit, especially at highly negative potentials. At -0.635 V vs RHE, the model predicted a partial current density of 2 mA cm^{-2} , whereas the measured value was 14 mA cm^{-2} . The poor fit may result from high onset potential of CH_4 , which was first detected at -0.605 V vs RHE.

The values of the fit parameters have been collected in Supplementary Table 1. With the used fitting procedure, α values were ≤ 1 for COER. With CH_4 , a reasonable

Figure 4: Experimental and simulated (a) partial current densities for major products, (b) partial current densities for minor products, (c) product selectivities and (d) cell voltage and CO conversion.

fit was only achieved for $\alpha \gg 1$, which explains the deviation. Despite the condition of $\alpha \leq 1$, it should still be remembered that the fit values represent the apparent kinetics of the process and only give a brief insight into the underlying physics of the process.

Good agreement between simulated and measured partial current densities translates into good agreement of selectivities (Figure 4c). The most significant deviations are CH_3COOH and H_2 , which are respectively overestimated and underestimated at less negative potentials.

The voltage-current curve (Figure 4d) also shows very good agreement with experimental data. In the lower current density range the simulated voltage is within 25-50 mV of the experimental data. Larger error of approx. 100 mV is found at the highest measured current. This may indicate an imperfectly reproduced overpotential distribution. It is likely that the ohmic losses are overestimated. The simulated CO conversion is also consistent with the experimental data. However, this is only after the conversion rates have been recalculated with the formula provided by the authors of the source data. Using the data found directly in the article, the model conversion rate is overestimated in the whole current density range.

The high conversion rates approaching 70% at the relatively low inlet flow of 1 sccm may suggest that the cell is approaching the mass-transfer limited regime. Increasing the inlet flow to the still low value of 2 sccm results in higher partial current densities (Figure 5), which is due to the greater availability of CO in the catalytic zone. Further increasing the flow rate has less of an effect for ethylene (Figure 5a) and ethanol (Figure 5b), but due the high value of fit reaction order γ , the increase of partial current density of propanol (Figure 5c) is larger. Nevertheless, an increase to 15 sccm translates into a decrease in the conversion rate to below 10%. These hold true under the assumption that the reaction kinetics remain constant under changing CO flow rate.

The dominant source of losses in the modelled system is cathodic overpotential (Figure 5d). The anodic overpotential is low because a highly optimized catalyst was used, with $\eta_{10} = 177$ mV and Tafel slope of 51.9 mV dec^{-1} [66]. In turn, ohmic losses are significant only at higher current densities and exceed 0.5 V at 200 mA cm^{-2} . At $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$, the cell resistance is 2.7 Ω , which consists primarily of the resistance of the anolyte in the porous anode $R_{\text{A-EL}}$ and the catholyte layer $R_{\text{C-EL}}$ (Figure 5e). The conductivity of electrolytes increases with temperature, so that an increase to 40°C translates into a decrease in resistance to 1.1 Ω . A further increase in temperature translates into a smaller decrease in resistance.

Figure 5: Partial current densities under CO inlet flow of 1, 2, 5 and 15 sccm for (a) C_2H_4 , (b) C_2H_5OH and (c) C_3H_7OH . (d) Voltage-current characteristics with the overpotential distribution. (e) Voltage-current characteristics and resistance breakdown for $T = 20, 40$ and $60^\circ C$. (f) The effect of electrolyte concentration on the cell voltage for $i = 100 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$.

An increase in electrolyte concentration also causes a decrease in ohmic losses and thus the cell voltage (Figure 5f). The effect is positive up to approx. 2 - 3 M. A further increase in C^{NaOH} causes a smaller increase in conductivity, which is offset by the an unfavourable shift in the half-cell reaction potentials due to the increased concentration of OH^- ions on the catalysts.

Even with favourable process and design parameters, the minimum voltage required to run the process is approximately 1.6-1.7 V. This voltage level is currently unattainable for commercially available solar cells. The simplest solution is therefore

to use the PV-EC configuration (Figure 1b), equipped with an external multi-cell solar panel. A typical SiSC achieves an open-circuit voltage U_{oc} of approximately 0.7 V [22], so the minimum number of cells in a series is 3. To operate with a single solar cell, which is desirable in PEC and PV-PEC systems (Figures 1c and 1d), the process voltage ought to decrease.

The solution may therefore lie in modifying the reactor not on the power supply side, but on the reaction side. A way to significantly reduce the anodic potential is to replace the OER with the EGOR (Figure 6a). The reversible potential of OER is 1.23 V and -0.334 V for EGOR to glycolic acid, and therefore the theoretical potential decrease is over 1.56 V. The reversible potential of the anodic reaction is lower than that of the cathodic ECOR, which means that the full-cell potential is negative (Figure 6b), demonstrating the EGOR is thermodynamically very favourable and that the cell could operate spontaneously (at $< \mu\text{mA cm}^{-2}$ levels). However, the high onset potential of EGOR (900-1000 mV with present catalysts) pushes the cell potential above reversible ECOR potential and external bias is required to operate at higher current densities. The potential is still lower than OER, and at 400 mA cm^{-2} the cell operates at potential lower by 0.578 V. The advantage of EGOR diminishes as the current increases. The much higher Tafel slope of EGOR ($150\text{-}200 \text{ mV dec}^{-1}$ with present catalysts) compared to OER suggests, that there is a current density above which OER is more favourable. The advantages of EGOR diminish more significantly for lower ethylene glycol concentrations. At 1 M, the EGOR offset decreases from 0.578 V at 400 mA cm^{-2} to 0.528 V at 800 mA cm^{-2} (difference of 50 mV), while for 0.25 M, the same doubling of current density decreases the advantage by 146 mV (from 0.543 to 0.397 V).

It should be noted that EGOR catalysts developed over the last few years are compared here to significantly more mature OER catalysts. The large onset potential of EGOR suggests that there is considerable room for improvement. The influence of these key catalyst parameters is shown in Figure 7a. The marked points correspond to EGOR catalysts available in the literature [29–32]. It should be noted, that the kinetics have been extracted from LSV curves for catalysts tested in three-electrode H-cell systems. However, the authors of [30] successfully demonstrated stable (50 hours) ethy-

a)

b)

Figure 6: (a) Half-cell potentials for OER and EGOR. (b) Cell potential (without resistance) at different current densities. The onset potential and Tafel slope of EGOR were assumed to be 900 mV and 200 mV dec^{-1} , respectively.

lene glycol oxidation at 100 mA cm^{-2} and 1.2 V in MEA. Therefore, it was assumed that the obtained data could also be used in a flow-cell system.

With advancements in catalyst design, the theoretical cell voltage could drop to

Figure 7: (a) Influence of catalyst parameters on the ECOR-EGOR cell potential at $i = 25, 100$ and 400 mA cm^{-2} , with and without ohmic losses. (b) Characteristics of the cooperation between OER- and EGOR-based COER reactor with SiSC and PSC. (c) Characteristics of the cooperation between the OER- and EGOR-based COER reactor with StPSC and photoanode. The fit parameters of equation (47) for individual photoelements are summarised in Supplementary Figure 1.

$\approx 1 - 1.2 \text{ V}$ at 25 mA cm^{-2} , to $1.3 - 1.5 \text{ V}$ at 100 mA cm^{-2} and to $\approx 1.8 - 2 \text{ V}$ at 400 mA cm^{-2} . Furthermore, most of the overpotential difference is due to ohmic losses, and the overpotential of the reaction itself is on the order of 100-200 mV. This highlights the need to use configurations with minimal resistance in order to fully extract the performance of the catalysts [15].

Improving the properties of catalysts could be an important step towards creating unbiased, solar-powered ECOR systems (Figure 7b). While SiSCs did not provide sufficient voltage to drive the process in the case of OER, EGOR enables unbiased operation, albeit at low current densities ($< 1 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$). PSCs offer great potential here, as they achieve higher U_{oc} . Modern, high-performance PSCs could enable the EGOR-based COER system to operate at current densities exceeding 5 mA cm^{-2} . Improving

the catalyst parameters would enable a significant increase in performance. An EGOR catalyst with a theoretical Tafel slope of 100 mV dec^{-1} and $\eta_{10} = 600 \text{ mV}$ could achieve current densities greater than 20 mA cm^{-2} with unbiased PSC.

Tandem solar cells, which can be used in the PV-PEC configuration (Figure 1d) are becoming increasingly popular. They involve the use of a semi-transparent solar cell and a photoelectrode. The advantage of this solution is the possibility of tuning the layers to selected wavelengths, for more optimized utilization of incident radiation.

Using only a semi-transparent perovskite solar cell (StPSC), the current density achieved for EGOR is 6 mA cm^{-2} (Figure 7c). By placing an additional photoanode behind the StPSC, a higher current density can be achieved, in this case 12 mA cm^{-2} . Another advantage of this solution is the higher voltage obtained. As the components are connected in series, U_{oc} is 1.73 V , which is sufficient for the reactor to operate even with OER on the anode ($<0.2 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$). However, for the tandem layout to demonstrate an advantage over the conventional system, the appropriate design of the photoelements is crucial. In the presented system, the StPSC's i_{sc} is significantly lower than the photoanode's i_{sc} , which means that at currents above 12 mA cm^{-2} , StPSC would operate in reverse bias, limiting the reactors performance. Furthermore, for the photoanode to work effectively, the StPSC must be sufficiently transparent in the relevant wavelength range. Otherwise, the more complex design would not be compensated for by higher performance.

The advantage of solar-powered devices, especially in PEC and PV-PEC configurations, applies to low current density range and devices that are not externally powered. In order for COER reactors to find industrial applications, the aim is to achieve a current densities of hundreds of mA cm^{-2} [39]. However, in this respect, solar-powered reactors in PEC and PV-PEC configurations do not offer any advantage in performance (Figure 8). Above i_{sc} , they can generate additional losses, which is why bypass diodes should be used. The advantages of PEC and PV-PEC devices can be seen in off-grid applications or in remote areas, as they can be used without external energy source. For the most favourable configuration (StPSC with photoanode), the current density is 12 mA cm^{-2} , with partial current densities for ethylene, ethanol and propanol being 6.55 , 1.23 and 1.27 mA cm^{-2} , respectively. However, this is only possible when using

Figure 8: Performance of selected, externally- and solar-powered ECOR configurations for external bias of 0 to 3 V.

EGOR.

In addition to enabling the process to be carried out without an external energy source on a small scale, EGOR can also reduce the energy consumption of the process on a large scale. Using 1 M ethylene glycol (and an appropriate catalyst), it was possible to obtain almost identical partial current densities for fuels (368 and 360 mA cm⁻² for ethylene, 108 and 105 mA cm⁻² for ethanol and 49.8 and 49.1 mA cm⁻² for propanol) at a voltage 0.5 V lower. This translates into energy savings of around 16%. An additional benefit here is the production of glycolic acid, a valuable compound that is in demand in the pharmaceutical and cosmetics industries. Its partial current density was 837 mA cm⁻² at 2.5 V, and this level of i has been demonstrated experimentally [30].

The appropriateness of using EGOR will also depend on the source of ethylene glycol. The use of pure substance may not be economically viable, and therefore alternative sources should be considered, such as alkaline hydrolysis of PET plastic. In addition, the separation of glycolic acid will also be a key aspect. The resulting mixture of aqueous electrolyte solution, unreacted ethylene glycol and glycolic acid (as well as potentially trace amounts of cathode products crossing the membrane) will require processing. Especially since highly concentrated C₂H₄O₃ has a significantly higher market price [67]. Furthermore, the energy required for separation will reduce the savings achieved by using EGOR instead of OER.

4. Summary and conclusions

Ethylene glycol oxidation is a promising method of improving the feasibility and sustainability of fuel production by CO electrolysis, especially in solar-powered systems. To study such system, we propose a simplified model of CO electrochemical reduction. Despite the simplifications applied, this model accurately reflects the results obtained experimentally. It may therefore be used in the study of EGOR applications in energy systems and industry.

The main sources of losses are activation overpotential and ohmic losses (at high currents). The former can be minimised through catalyst development, while the latter

depends largely on the properties of the electrolytes. Replacing OER with ethylene glycol oxidation may also be an appealing strategy for reducing the energy intensity of the process. The achievable voltage reduction with EGOR is ≈ 0.5 V with modern catalysts. However, there is considerable room for improvement, as the onset potentials for EGOR are currently about 900 mV higher than its reversible potential. In addition to the reduced energy consumption of the process (by approx. 16% at 400 mA cm^{-2}), an additional advantage here is the production of glycolic acid. On the other hand, the need to separate glycolic acid from liquid products will reduce the advantage of EGOR.

Reduced operating voltage under EGOR may be significant for the development of solar-powered ECOR systems. Modern single-junction solar cells do not provide sufficient voltage to run ECOR. It would therefore be necessary to use tandem or multi-junction systems or connect the cells in series. By using EGOR on the anode, the required voltage drops to the level currently achieved by perovskite solar cells. This allows the unbiased process to be carried out at current densities exceeding 5 mA cm^{-2} . Using more advanced configurations, such as tandem PV-PEC using semi-transparent perovskite solar cells, current densities can exceed 10 mA cm^{-2} .

The advantages of PEC and PV-PEC devices are only present in the low current density range. At high currents, the photoelements would operate in reverse bias, potentially causing losses. In the case of industrial production of sustainable solar fuels, it is therefore more advisable to use the PV-EC layout. This allows for flexible control of the configuration and surface area of the photovoltaic system. It should be then remembered that it is necessary to select a PV system that will operate as close as possible to the MPP and maintain the desired distribution of reaction products.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Janusz Kotowicz: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Writing - review & editing; **Dominik Hulak:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing - original draft; **Leszek Remiorz:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Super-

vision, Writing - review & editing; **Mateusz Brzęczek**: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Writing - review & editing; **Łukasz Böhm**: Software, Writing - review & editing; **Oliwia Baszceńska**: Visualization, Writing - review & editing; **Katarzyna Janusz-Szymańska**: Resources, Writing - review & editing; **Kamil Niesporek**: Visualization, Writing - review & editing

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data availability

The data supporting this article have been included as part of the Supplementary Information.

Acknowledgements

This project is funded by the European Union (No. 101172764). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

- [1] Hori Y, Wakebe H, Tsukamoto T, Koga O. Electrocatalytic process of CO selectivity in electrochemical reduction of CO₂ at metal electrodes in aqueous media. *Electrochimica Acta* 1994;39:1833–9. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4686\(94\)85172-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4686(94)85172-7).
- [2] Sultan S, Lee H, Park S, Kim MM, Yoon A, Choi H, et al. Interface rich CuO/Al₂CuO₄ surface for selective ethylene production from electrochemical CO₂ conversion. *Energy Environ Sci* 2022;15:2397–409. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1EE03861C>.

- [3] Chen C, Yan X, Liu S, Wu Y, Wan Q, Sun X, et al. Highly Efficient Electroreduction of CO₂ to C₂+ Alcohols on Heterogeneous Dual Active Sites. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 2020;59:16459–64. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202006847>.
- [4] De R, Gonglach S, Paul S, Haas M, Sreejith SS, Gerschel P, et al. Electrocatalytic Reduction of CO₂ to Acetic Acid by a Molecular Manganese Corrole Complex. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 2020;59:10527–34. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202000601>.
- [5] Barecka MH, Ager JW, Lapkin AA. Economically viable CO₂ electroreduction embedded within ethylene oxide manufacturing. *Energy Environ Sci* 2021;14:1530–43. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0EE03310C>.
- [6] Rabinowitz J, Kanan M. The future of low-temperature carbon dioxide electrolysis depends on solving one basic problem. *Nature Communications* 2020;11:5231. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-19135-8>.
- [7] Verma S, Hamasaki Y, Kim C, Huang W, Lu S, Jhong H-RM, et al. Insights into the Low Overpotential Electroreduction of CO₂ to CO on a Supported Gold Catalyst in an Alkaline Flow Electrolyzer. *ACS Energy Lett* 2018;3:193–8. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acseenergylett.7b01096>.
- [8] Leonard ME, Clarke LE, Forner-Cuenca A, Brown SM, Brushett FR. Investigating Electrode Flooding in a Flowing Electrolyte, Gas-Fed Carbon Dioxide Electrolyzer. *ChemSusChem* 2020;13:400–11. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201902547>.
- [9] Martić N, Reller C, Macauley C, Löffler M, Reichert AM, Reichbauer T, et al. Ag₂Cu₂O₃ – a catalyst template material for selective electroreduction of CO to C₂+ products. *Energy Environ Sci* 2020;13:2993–3006. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0EE01100B>.
- [10] Jouny M, Luc W, Jiao F. High-rate electroreduction of carbon monoxide to multi-

- carbon products. *Nat Catal* 2018;1:748–55. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41929-018-0133-2>.
- [11] Romero Cuellar NS, Wiesner-Fleischer K, Fleischer M, Rucki A, Hinrichsen O. Advantages of CO over CO₂ as reactant for electrochemical reduction to ethylene, ethanol and n-propanol on gas diffusion electrodes at high current densities. *Electrochimica Acta* 2019;307:164–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2019.03.142>.
- [12] Verdaguier-Casadevall A, Li CW, Johansson TP, Scott SB, McKeown JT, Kumar M, et al. Probing the Active Surface Sites for CO Reduction on Oxide-Derived Copper Electrocatalysts. *J Am Chem Soc* 2015;137:9808–11. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.5b06227>.
- [13] Cheng W-H, Richter MH, Sullivan I, Larson DM, Xiang C, Brunschwig BS, et al. CO₂ Reduction to CO with 19% Efficiency in a Solar-Driven Gas Diffusion Electrode Flow Cell under Outdoor Solar Illumination. *ACS Energy Lett* 2020;5:470–6. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenergylett.9b02576>.
- [14] Li CW, Ciston J, Kanan MW. Electroreduction of carbon monoxide to liquid fuel on oxide-derived nanocrystalline copper. *Nature* 2014;508:504–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13249>.
- [15] Monis Ayyub M, Kormányos A, Endrődi B, Janáky C. Electrochemical carbon monoxide reduction at high current density: Cell configuration matters. *Chemical Engineering Journal* 2024;490:151698. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2024.151698>.
- [16] Wang X, Ou P, Ozden A, Hung S-F, Tam J, Gabardo CM, et al. Efficient electrosynthesis of n-propanol from carbon monoxide using a Ag–Ru–Cu catalyst. *Nat Energy* 2022;7:170–6. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-021-00967-7>.
- [17] Ripatti DS, Veltman TR, Kanan MW. Carbon Monoxide Gas Diffusion Electrolysis that Produces Concentrated C₂ Products with High Single-Pass Conversion. *Joule* 2019;3:240–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2018.10.007>.

- [18] Andrei V, Reuillard B, Reisner E. Bias-free solar syngas production by integrating a molecular cobalt catalyst with perovskite–BiVO₄ tandems. *Nat Mater* 2020;19:189–94. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41563-019-0501-6>.
- [19] Li C, Wang T, Liu B, Chen M, Li A, Zhang G, et al. Photoelectrochemical CO₂ reduction to adjustable syngas on grain-boundary-mediated a-Si/TiO₂/Au photocathodes with low onset potentials. *Energy Environ Sci* 2019;12:923–8. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8EE02768D>.
- [20] Gurudayal G, Beeman JW, Bullock J, Wang H, Eichhorn J, Towle C, et al. Si photocathode with Ag-supported dendritic Cu catalyst for CO₂ reduction. *Energy Environ Sci* 2019;12:1068–77. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8EE03547D>.
- [21] Ban H, Park J, Yun J, Ma S, Jang G, Goh S, et al. Chemically Stable Semitransparent Perovskite Solar Cells with High Hydrogen Generation Rates Based on Photovoltaic–Photoelectrochemical Tandem Cells. *Advanced Photonics Research* 2022;3:2100317. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adpr.202100317>.
- [22] Lin H, Yang M, Ru X, Wang G, Yin S, Peng F, et al. Silicon heterojunction solar cells with up to 26.81% efficiency achieved by electrically optimized nanocrystalline-silicon hole contact layers. *Nat Energy* 2023;8:789–99. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-023-01255-2>.
- [23] Lu J, Lin X, Jiao X, Gengenbach T, Scully AD, Jiang L, et al. Interfacial benzenethiol modification facilitates charge transfer and improves stability of cm-sized metal halide perovskite solar cells with up to 20% efficiency. *Energy Environ Sci* 2018;11:1880–9. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8EE00754C>.
- [24] Xu Z, Guo Z, Li H, Zhou Y, Liu Z, Wang K, et al. Efficient and stable inverted MA/Br-free 2D/3D perovskite solar cells enabled by α -to- δ phase transition inhibition and crystallization modulation. *Energy Environ Sci* 2025;18:1354–65. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4EE04136D>.
- [25] Gurudayal, Bullock J, Srankó DF, Towle CM, Lum Y, Hettick M, et al. Efficient

- solar-driven electrochemical CO₂ reduction to hydrocarbons and oxygenates. *Energy Environ Sci* 2017;10:2222–30. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7EE01764B>.
- [26] Chen X, Chen J, Chen H, Zhang Q, Li J, Cui J, et al. Promoting water dissociation for efficient solar driven CO₂ electroreduction via improving hydroxyl adsorption. *Nat Commun* 2023;14:751. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-36263-z>.
- [27] Chen YX, Lavacchi A, Miller HA, Bevilacqua M, Filippi J, Innocenti M, et al. Nanotechnology makes biomass electrolysis more energy efficient than water electrolysis. *Nat Commun* 2014;5:4036. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms5036>.
- [28] Na J, Seo B, Kim J, Lee CW, Lee H, Hwang YJ, et al. General techno-economic analysis for electrochemical coproduction coupling carbon dioxide reduction with organic oxidation. *Nat Commun* 2019;10:5193. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-12744-y>.
- [29] Si D, Xiong B, Chen L, Shi J. Highly selective and efficient electrocatalytic synthesis of glycolic acid in coupling with hydrogen evolution. *Chem Catalysis* 2021;1:941–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cheecat.2021.08.001>.
- [30] Liu F, Gao X, Shi R, Guo Z, Tse ECM, Chen Y. Concerted and Selective Electrooxidation of Polyethylene-Terephthalate-Derived Alcohol to Glycolic Acid at an Industry-Level Current Density over a Pd-Ni(OH)₂ Catalyst. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 2023;62:e202300094. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202300094>.
- [31] Ren T, Duan Z, Wang H, Yu H, Deng K, Wang Z, et al. Electrochemical Co-Production of Ammonia and Biodegradable Polymer Monomer Glycolic Acid via the Co-Electrolysis of Nitrate Wastewater and Waste Plastic. *ACS Catal* 2023;13:10394–404. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.3c02740>.
- [32] Cheng J, Tu Y, Xiang Y, Ni J, Guo T, Huang X, et al. Anti-poisoning of CO and carbonyl species over Pd catalysts during the electrooxidation of ethylene glycol to glycolic acid at elevated current density. *Chem Sci* 2025;16:4303–10. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4SC08579E>.

- [33] Barredo A, Asueta A, Amundarain I, Leivar J, Miguel-Fernández R, Arnaiz S, et al. Chemical recycling of monolayer PET tray waste by alkaline hydrolysis. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* 2023;11:109823. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.109823>.
- [34] Han J, Zuo J, Zillante G, Chang R, Du L. A systematic review of PET circularity technologies and management strategies: Challenges and future directions. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 2025;219:108280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2025.108280>.
- [35] Weng L-C, Bell AT, Weber AZ. Towards membrane-electrode assembly systems for CO₂ reduction: a modeling study. *Energy Environ Sci* 2019;12:1950–68. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9EE00909D>.
- [36] Weng L-C, Bell AT, Weber AZ. A systematic analysis of Cu-based membrane-electrode assemblies for CO₂ reduction through multiphysics simulation. *Energy Environ Sci* 2020;13:3592–606. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0EE01604G>.
- [37] Jiang Y, Bi T, Cheng M, Xue R, Shen S, Yan X, et al. Parameter sensitivity analysis for CO₂ electrochemical reduction electrolyzer. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2025;100:1291–300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.12.174>.
- [38] Wang H, Leung DYC, Xuan J. Modeling of a microfluidic electrochemical cell for CO₂ utilization and fuel production. *Applied Energy* 2013;102:1057–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2012.06.020>.
- [39] Alkayyali T, Zargartalebi M, Ozden A, Arabyarmohammadi F, Dorakhan R, Edwards JP, et al. Pathways to reduce the energy cost of carbon monoxide electroreduction to ethylene. *Joule* 2024;8:1478–500. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2024.02.014>.
- [40] Zhang J, Jiang H, Zhao X, Liu Z, Li L, Ding W, et al. Energy Efficiency Limit in CO-to-Ethylene Electroreduction and the Method to Ad-

- vance Toward. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 2025;64:e202502690. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202502690>.
- [41] Abdin Z, Webb CJ, Gray EMacA. Modelling and simulation of a proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyser cell. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2015;40:13243–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.07.129>.
- [42] Marangio F, Santarelli M, Cali M. Theoretical model and experimental analysis of a high pressure PEM water electrolyser for hydrogen production. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2009;34:1143–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2008.11.083>.
- [43] Chmielniak T, Remiorz L. Entropy analysis of hydrogen production in electrolytic processes. *Energy* 2020;211:118468. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.118468>.
- [44] Bae D, Pedersen T, Seger B, Malizia M, Kuznetsov A, Hansen O, et al. Back-illuminated Si photocathode: a combined experimental and theoretical study for photocatalytic hydrogen evolution. *Energy Environ Sci* 2015;8:650–60. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C4EE03723E>.
- [45] Elliott JR, Diky V, Knotts TA, Wilding WV. *Properties of Gases and Liquids*. 6th Edition. McGraw-Hill Education; 2023.
- [46] Casalini T, Rossi F, Santoro M, Perale G. Structural Characterization of Poly-L-lactic Acid (PLLA) and Poly(glycolic acid)(PGA) Oligomers. *IJMS* 2011;12:3857–70. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms12063857>.
- [47] Ternström G, Sjöstrand A, Aly G, Jernqvist Å. Mutual Diffusion Coefficients of Water + Ethylene Glycol and Water + Glycerol Mixtures. *J Chem Eng Data* 1996;41:876–9. <https://doi.org/10.1021/je9501705>.
- [48] Pratt KC, Wakeham WA. The mutual diffusion coefficient for binary mixtures of water and the isomers of propanol. *Proc R Soc Lond A* 1975;342:401–19. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.1975.0031>.

- [49] Gas Diffusion Layers (GDL) - AvCarb Material Solutions. AvCarb. <https://www.avcarb.com/products/gas-diffusion-layers-gdl/> (accessed September 24, 2025).
- [50] Sander R. Compilation of Henry's law constants (version 5.0.0) for water as solvent. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 2023;23:10901–2440. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-23-10901-2023>.
- [51] Weisenberger S, Schumpe A. Estimation of gas solubilities in salt solutions at temperatures from 273 K to 363 K. *AIChE Journal* 1996;42:298–300. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.690420130>.
- [52] Schweiss R, Meiser C, Damjanovic T, Galbiati I, Haak N. SIGRACET® Gas Diffusion Layers for PEM Fuel Cells, Electrolyzers and Batteries (White Paper). 2016.
- [53] Wang S, Deng X, Wang J, Zhu Y. Experimental measurements of effective electrical conductivities and electrical contact resistances in proton exchange membrane fuel cells. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2025;103:556–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2025.01.289>.
- [54] Marr C, Li X. An engineering model of proton exchange membrane fuel cell performance. *ARI* 1997;50:190–200. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s007770050014>.
- [55] Ameri A. Density, Refractive Index, Electrical Conductivity, pH, and FT-IR and UV-Vis Spectra of Potassium Carbonate–Potassium Bicarbonate–Water System. *J Chem Eng Data* 2025;70:766–86. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jced.4c00489>.
- [56] Gilliam R, Graydon J, Kirk D, Thorpe S. A review of specific conductivities of potassium hydroxide solutions for various concentrations and temperatures. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2007;32:359–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2006.10.062>.
- [57] Landesfeind J, Hattendorff J, Ehrl A, Wall WA, Gasteiger HA. Tortuosity Determination of Battery Electrodes and Separators by Impedance Spectroscopy. *J Electrochem Soc* 2016;163:A1373. <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.1141607jes>.

- [58] Tjaden B, Cooper SJ, Brett DJ, Kramer D, Shearing PR. On the origin and application of the Bruggeman correlation for analysing transport phenomena in electrochemical systems. *Current Opinion in Chemical Engineering* 2016;12:44–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coche.2016.02.006>.
- [59] Thermal conductivity and electrical resistivity of type 316 stainless steel from 0 to 1800f, <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/19650024830> (accessed September 24, 2025).
- [60] Buchner R, Hefter G, May PM, Sipos P. Dielectric relaxation of dilute aqueous NaOH, NaAl(OH)₄ and NaB(OH)₄. *Journal of Physical Chemistry B* 1999;103:11186–90.
- [61] Jensen JO, Aili D, Hansen MK, Li Q, Bjerrum NJ, Christensen E. (Invited) A Stability Study of Alkali Doped PBI Membranes for Alkaline Electrolyzer Cells. *ECS Trans* 2014;64:1175. <https://doi.org/10.1149/06403.1175ecst>.
- [62] Nickel Foam. <https://www.goodfellow.com/eu/nickel-sizes-foam-group> (accessed September 24, 2025).
- [63] Walker G. Evaluating MPPT Converter Topologies Using a Matlab PV Model. *Journal of Electrical & Electronics Engineering, Australia* 2001;21:49–55. <https://doi.org/10.3316/informit.537020271845747>.
- [64] Guillemoles J-F, Kirchartz T, Cahen D, Rau U. Guide for the perplexed to the Shockley–Queisser model for solar cells. *Nat Photonics* 2019;13:501–5. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41566-019-0479-2>.
- [65] Boyd M, Klein S, Reindl D, Dougherty B. Evaluation and Validation of Equivalent Circuit Photovoltaic Solar Cell Performance Models. *Journal of Solar Energy Engineering* 2011;133. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4003584>.
- [66] Zhou H, Yu F, Sun J, He R, Chen S, Chu C-W, et al. Highly active catalyst derived from a 3D foam of Fe(PO₃)₂/Ni₂P for extremely efficient water oxidation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 2017;114:5607–11. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1701562114>.

- [67] Zhou X, Zha M, Cao J, Yan H, Feng X, Chen D, et al. Glycolic Acid Production from Ethylene Glycol via Sustainable Biomass Energy: Integrated Conceptual Process Design and Comparative Techno-economic–Society–Environment Analysis. *ACS Sustainable Chem Eng* 2021;9:10948–62. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.1c03717>.